

INTEGRATING LOCAL CULTURAL WISDOM INTO ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR: THE ROLE OF ‘JHUNG ROJHUNG’ AMONG VILLAGE OFFICIALS IN MADURA

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Abstract

The integration of local cultural values into organisational behaviour studies remains an underexplored but essential domain, particularly within the governance structures of the Global South. In Madura, Indonesia, the cultural concept of *Jhung Rojhung*, a deeply rooted norm encompassing respect, moral integrity, and social responsibility, continues to shape how village officials conduct themselves within their organisations. This study investigates how *Jhung Rojhung* influences organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the village apparatus in Padelegan Village, Pamekasan Regency. Employing a qualitative case study approach, data were gathered through in-depth interviews, participant observations, and document analysis. Thematic analysis revealed four major insights: (1) *Jhung Rojhung* acts as a moral compass that internalises a sense of duty among village staff; (2) it fosters altruistic behaviour driven by cultural obligation rather than formal rules; (3) it reinforces loyalty and conscientiousness, reflecting strong elements of OCB; and (4) it cultivates social harmony and civic virtue through active community participation. The findings suggest that understanding OCB in village governance requires taking into account the cultural substratum that underpins formal structures. Theoretically, this study contributes to the expansion of OCB frameworks by integrating local knowledge. Practically, it draws attention to the need to embed cultural values into policy design, recruitment, and the training of village officials.

Keywords: Organisational Citizenship Behaviour, Local Wisdom, Jhung Rojhung, Village Governance, Cultural Behaviour, and Madura.

1. INTRODUCTION

In a complex and challenging public organisation landscape, civil servants' work behaviour cannot be explained solely by formal regulations and structural incentives [1]. Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB) has attracted widespread attention in organisational studies because it refers to voluntary and implicitly requested behaviour that supports organisational effectiveness. This concept is particularly important in the context of public services at the grassroots level, such as village officials, where successful governance depends heavily on loyalty, social sensitivity, and active participation beyond formal duties [2], [3], [4]. Amidst the increasingly complex challenges of village development, it is important to understand the factors that drive village officials to display OCB. In the Indonesian context, local culture has a major influence on these values and work practices. However, universalistic perspectives rooted in Western contexts tend to dominate the academic literature on OCB [5]. OCB models developed in the West often ignore the role of local values in shaping workplace behaviour [6]. In fact, in a society such as Indonesia, which is rich in culture, many work values and social ethics are alive and serve as guidelines for the actions of local government officials [7]. One of

the distinctive values that has not been widely highlighted in scientific literature is "Jhung Rojhung", a Madurese cultural concept that reflects honour, loyalty, and a spirit of devotion to duty and community. This value is believed to be a moral and social driving force that influences how Madura village officials carry out their duties, including demonstrating OCB behaviors such as mutual assistance, maintaining social harmony, and showing a high sense of responsibility. Regrettably, research on the correlation between local cultural values (Jhung Rojhung) and organisational behaviour remains severely limited. Studies on OCB in Indonesia have yet to explore the cultural dynamics rooted in the local value systems. We need to bridge this important knowledge gap [8], [9], [10]. Moreover, in the context of Madura, which has a strong cultural identity and a social system with a strong sense of honour and hierarchy, there have been few studies that systematically document how these values shape organisational behaviour, especially in the context of public services at the village level. The dominance of Western approaches that emphasise individualism, psychological contracts, and rational efficiency makes it important to develop an alternative theoretical framework that values local wisdom as the foundation for shaping workplace behaviour. [11], [12].

Based on this background, this study aims to examine how the local cultural value of *Jhung Rojhung* shapes the OCB behaviour of village officials in Madura, with a case study in Padelegan Village, Pademawu District, Pamekasan Regency. This study seeks to answer the following main question: How does the cultural concept of "Jhung Rojhung" shape the organisational citizenship behaviour of village officials in Madura? Focussing on values internalised in social relations and local power structures, this study explores how Jhung Rojhung not only becomes a work ethic but also a moral framework in the daily decision-making and actions of village officials, both in serving the community and in their relationships with one another. This study has important theoretical and practical implications. Theoretically, this research contributes to expanding our understanding of OCB from a cultural perspective by integrating local wisdom as a determinant of organisational behaviour [13], [14] The finding is important for efforts to dismantle universalistic assumptions that have long dominated management theory and organisational behaviour. In practical terms, this study provides local governments, village facilitators, and training institutions with a profound understanding of the importance of local cultural values in building effective and integrity-based village governance [15]By making *Jhung Rojhung* the basis of values in the development of village officials, it is hoped that work practices will be established that are not only efficient, but also dignified and contextual in accordance with the cultural roots of the community. Thus, this study not only enriches the literature on organisational culture and OCB but also serves as a bridge between global knowledge and local practices. In an era of decentralisation and village empowerment, understanding cultural dynamics, such as Jhung Rojhung, is key to building a strong and responsive village governance system based on the community's noble values.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review aims to establish a theoretical and contextual foundation for understanding how local cultural values, such as Jhung Rojhung's, can influence the organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) of village officials. This section discusses four main dimensions: the concept and dimension of OCB, the relationship between culture and organisational behaviour, the role of local wisdom in Indonesian public governance, and the distinctive characteristics of Jhung Rojhung as a Madurese cultural construct.

1. Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The concept of organisational citizenship Behaviour was first introduced by Dennis Organ in the 1980s as a form of individual behaviour within an organisation that is voluntary, not directly rewarded through a formal reward system, but that collectively improves the effectiveness of the organisation. [16]. Formal job descriptions do not include OCB behaviours; yet they contribute to a healthy and efficient work environment. The author argues that organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) encompasses five main dimensions that form the foundation of positive employee behaviour beyond formal duties. The first is altruism, which is the attitude of helping colleagues without expecting anything in return, especially in helping them complete urgent tasks. The second is conscientiousness, which reflects a high level of discipline and responsibility, even beyond the minimum standards expected by an organisation. The third dimension is civic virtue, which means active participation in organisational life and concern for the progress and development of the organisation as a whole. Fourth, courtesy is manifested in efforts to maintain harmonious interpersonal relationships and avoid potential conflicts. Finally, sportsmanship is the ability to tolerate less-than-ideal conditions within the organisation without complaining or displaying negative attitudes. Various studies have indicated that OCB is relevant in the public sector, particularly because government bureaucracies often face resource constraints and high-pressure public service. (From Geus et al., 2020a; Y. Studies in the social services, health, and education sectors show that OCB improves service quality, builds public trust, and encourages synergy among employees [17], [18], [19]. However, most of these studies are still rooted in individualistic cultural contexts and Western management systems [20], [21]. Therefore, expanding the analytical framework to include collectivist cultures such as Indonesia has become urgent.

2. Culture and Organizational Behavior

Culture is an important variable for understanding organisational behaviour, as it shapes collective values, norms, and expectations regarding individual actions (Brahm & Poblete, 2024; Fernandes et al., 2023; M.-T. Wang & Hofkens, 2020). Hofstede (1980) emphasized that national cultural differences influence communication styles, perceptions of authority, and work motivation. In his dimensions, Indonesian culture tends to score high on collectivism, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance, implying a strong role for hierarchy, loyalty, and social harmony in organizational interactions [25], [26]. Organisational culture is a layered structure that encompasses basic assumptions, explicit values, and behavioural artefacts. In the context of rural communities in Indonesia, cultural values are often unwritten but serve as strong guidelines for decision-making and working relationships (Rochmansjah & Saputra, 2024).

The relationship between seniority, loyalty to leaders, and collective responsibility forms an informal framework that governs village officials' behaviour. Local studies are beginning to show how cultural values such as cooperation, modesty, and obedience to informal authority influence the way rural communities work and make decisions (Assoratgoon & Kantabutra, 2023; Luneva, 2022). However, there are still hardly any studies that have explicitly linked these values to the dimensions of OCB. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop a more contextual understanding of how local work culture interacts with modern organisational theory.

3. Local Wisdom and Governance in Indonesia

Local wisdom is a system of values and knowledge that grows and develops within a particular community through historical experiences, social environments, and daily practices. In the Indonesian context, local wisdom often serves as the ethical and moral foundation for village administration, although it is not always formally documented [29]. Research in the field of village governance shows that the success of public policy at the local level is largely determined by social involvement stemming from local values (Harahap & Hamka, 2023; Medan et al., 2025). For instance, certain Indigenous communities adhere more strictly to customary norms than to formal state regulations. This demonstrates that studies of public organisation behaviour in Indonesia cannot ignore local value systems [32]. In the context of Madura, the social system is strongly influenced by three main principles: loyalty, honour (self-respect), and social hierarchy. Loyalty to leaders and groups is considered a form of honor and honesty [33]. Honour is not merely a matter of status but rather a moral reputation inherent in a person's social actions. The social hierarchy is strictly maintained, and respect for seniors and community leaders is a strong ethical principle. These values are likely to play an important role in shaping OCB behaviours in the village apparatus, particularly in terms of compliance, participation, and social commitment.

4. Jhung Rojhung as Cultural Construct

Jhung Rojhung is a unique expression in Madurese culture that is difficult to translate literally but has a profound meaning in the social life of the community. Literally, this term refers to the act or attitude of "maintaining respect" or "appreciating sincerely and responsibly." [34] In social practice, Jhung Rojhung has become a symbol of moral integrity, social responsibility, and devotion to others, both in the context of family relations and public service [35]. The core values of Jhung Rojhung emphasise noble principles that guide behaviour and action [36]. Selfless dedication is the main foundation, manifested as a form of respect for the position or office held. Leaders and the community view loyalty as a reflection of strong integrity, demonstrating a commitment to maintaining trust and unity. In addition, Jhung Rojhung upholds the avoidance of open conflict as a form of responsibility for maintaining harmony in the social environment of the village. Work is seen as more than just a means of earning a living; it is considered a field of honor a place where one can make a contribution and earn self-respect through dedication and quality of work [37]. These values form a moral framework that governs individual behaviour, strengthens solidarity, and fosters mutual respect (Gusti et al., 2022). In the context of village organisations, Jhung Rojhung serves as an unwritten code of ethics that governs the behaviour of officials (Setiani et al., 2022). Village officials often represent these values by demonstrating high discipline, responding to residents' needs, and upholding politeness in communication. Jhung Rojhung also serves as a social tool for assessing whether someone is trustworthy and can be given responsibility within the village structure (J. Li et al., 2025). Furthermore, this value has a strategic position in bridging the gap between formal authority (the state) and social authority (culture). Officials who work according to the principles of Jhung Rojhung tend not only to carry out their duties based on regulations, but also with moral considerations and respect for citizens as part of the community. [41] Thus, Jhung Rojhung can be understood as a cultural foundation that reinforces the emergence of OCB dimensions such as altruism, conscientiousness, and civic virtue.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach with a case study design, which was chosen to explore in depth how the cultural values of Jhung Rojhung shape organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) in the village administration. This approach is considered the most appropriate for understanding the social context and meaning created by participants in a particular social environment, which cannot be adequately explained through quantitative approaches [42]. Case studies as a design strategy allow researchers to explore phenomena holistically in real-life contexts, especially when the boundaries between the phenomena and context are not entirely clear. This study does not aim to produce statistical generalisations but rather build a contextual and in-depth understanding of the relationship between local culture and organisational behaviour at the village level [43]. The location of this study was Padelegan Village, Pademawu Subdistrict, Pamekasan Regency, East Java Province. This village was selected as the study site because it has a complete village government structure, a rich social history, and strong preservation of Madurese cultural values, including the daily practices of its village officials. Within the case study framework, the village is treated as a bounded system, a social system with geographical, institutional, and cultural boundaries that can be observed in a focused way. This research was conducted with the consideration that the value of Jhung Rojhung is not only present in cultural discourse but also reflected in actions, social relations, and the work practices of village officials in the local environment.

The participants in this study consisted of village officials, including the village head, village secretary, hamlet head, and administrative staff who performed public service functions. Participants were selected using purposive sampling, which is a deliberate selection based on specific criteria relevant to the research objectives of this study. These criteria include a minimum of two years of work experience in village administration, active involvement in community service activities, and recognition by residents as a respected figure or role model in the community. The number of participants was adjusted according to the principle of information saturation, that is, until the data obtained showed recurring thematic patterns and did not reveal any significant new findings.

Data were collected through in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and documentation. In-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted to allow for the free exploration of participants' experiences and views regarding the value of Jhung Rojhung and how it influences their work behaviour. Interviews were conducted in Indonesian and Madurese, depending on the participants' comfort level, using an approach that respected local norms of politeness and social structure. Participatory observation was conducted by directly watching interactions between village officials and between officials and residents during various service activities and village meetings. The documentation included meeting minutes, organisational structures, and internal village policies related to work values and service ethics.

Ethical considerations were paramount in the conduct of this study. All participants were informed of the purpose and benefits of the study and were given the right to refuse or withdraw from participation at any time, without consequences. Informed consent was obtained, either verbally or in writing, according to the participants' preferences. Researchers maintained the confidentiality of participants' identities by using codes or pseudonyms in all transcripts and publications. Member checking, which involved asking participants to confirm the researcher's interpretation of the interview results, further strengthened the data validity. Additionally, data

triangulation was employed by comparing information from various sources and methods to ensure the consistency of the findings.

Data analysis was conducted using the thematic analysis approach developed by Braun and Clarke [44]. The stages of analysis include (1) transcription and repeated reading of interview data and observation notes, (2) initial coding of units of meaning, (3) grouping codes into initial themes, (4) reviewing and refining themes, (5) defining and naming themes, and (6) writing the analysis narrative. The analysis was conducted iteratively; that is, by continuously linking the data to the socio-cultural context and the OCB theoretical framework. In this stage, attention is given to how participants articulate the value of *Jhung Rojhung* in concrete actions that align with OCB dimensions, such as altruism, conscientiousness, and civic virtue.

The researcher's position in this study underwent critical reflection as part of methodological integrity. The researcher has an academic background and work experience in education and community development, as well as a basic understanding of the Madurese culture. However, the researcher is aware of the possibility of bias in perception and interpretation, especially in understanding local cultural expressions that are rich in symbolic meanings. Therefore, the researcher strives to maintain reflexive awareness of their position and influence in the research process by keeping a reflective journal, discussing with key informants, and retesting interpretations through a participatory approach. This approach is important so that the research results not only reflect the researcher's perspective but also truly capture the living meanings among participants.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. Finding

Jhung Rojhung as Moral Compass

In Madurese society, the value of *Jhung Rojhung* is not merely an ethical rule but a moral compass that guides the way people think, behave, and act. In the context of village administration, this value manifests as an internal standard that shapes perceptions of responsibility and duty far beyond the boundaries of formal job descriptions. Based on in-depth interviews and field observations in Padelegan Village, it is evident that *Jhung Rojhung* regulates interpersonal relationships and serves as the foundation of the moral responsibility of village officials towards the community, their positions, and themselves.

For the village officials participating in this study, serving the community is never considered merely an administrative duty. Many stated that "maintaining honour" was the main reason behind their dedication rather than simply receiving financial rewards or regulatory pressure. This concept of "honour" refers to the profound meaning of *Jhung Rojhung*, which states that a person will feel ashamed and uneasy if they neglect their community duties. In this understanding, responsibility is not seen as an order from a superior but as a trust that is directly linked to one's personal reputation and self-esteem in the eyes of the community.

Their behaviour, which demonstrates punctuality, responsiveness in resolving residents' complaints, and openness to public complaints, reflects this. Some officials even recounted how they remained involved in community affairs outside of working hours, including social activities or during times of disaster. When asked why they do things that are not written in their job descriptions, their answer always comes back to the principle of "if it is not done, it is

not worthy of a trusted person." This response reflects that their actions are guided by an internal value system rooted in Jhung Rojhung rather than mere bureaucratic logic.

This perception of responsibility demonstrates the depth of cultural meaning in shaping the OCB. The value of Jhung Rojhung strongly internalises the conscientiousness dimension of OCB, which includes responsibility, discipline, and commitment to tasks. Researchers have observed how village officials treat their work as part of their moral identity. When mistakes or delays occurred in service delivery, they felt personally failed, not merely as workers. Emotional reactions, such as feeling ashamed or anxious, did not stem from reprimands from superiors but from internal moral pressure rooted in the culture.

In addition, the values of Jhung Rojhung influence how its members understand power relations and hierarchy. A village head stated that in exercising his authority, he must remain humble because "sitting at the top is not for being arrogant, but for setting an example." In this case, Jhung Rojhung serves as a moral guide to avoid abusing authority and maintain harmonious and dignified relations with residents. This demonstrates Jhung Rojhung's contribution to the civic virtue dimension of OCB, where individuals are actively involved in maintaining integrity and communal life within the organisation.

Thus, Jhung Rojhung is not only a normative framework that shapes collective consciousness, but it also functions as an individual moral compass that encourages responsible, honest, and dedicated behaviour. These values indirectly create a strong and effective social control mechanism that replaces the role of formal surveillance systems. Village officials do not require a bureaucratic system of sanctions to comply with their duties; a sense of shame and loss of honour is sufficient to motivate them to act appropriately. This is what makes Jhung Rojhung a unique and contextual driver of OCB in the Madurese culture.

Cultural Obligation and Altruism

One of the main findings of this study is that Jhung Rojhung fosters a deep sense of altruism among village officials. Altruism, the main dimension of OCB, refers to actions that help fellow workers or members of an organisation without expecting anything in return. In the context of Padelegan Village, this altruistic behaviour is not merely a personal expression but part of a cultural obligation that is socially institutionalised through the values of Jhung Rojhung. In interviews, village officials often express that helping others is part of "ajhâbân," which means maintaining personal and social honour. This means that helping others is not only an act of kindness but also a moral investment that strengthens one's social position within the community. When someone is unwilling to help, they are not only considered rude but also seen as having no value in the Maduresian social structure, which emphasises collectivism, mutual respect, and interconnectedness. A village secretary stated, "It is better to be a little tired than to feel guilty for letting residents suffer."

Field observations show that village officials engage in many altruistic behaviours without being formally requested to do so. They help residents with important documents, pick up elderly residents who are unable to come to the village hall, and even mediate conflicts between residents outside working hours. These actions are considered part of their dedication and not as additional work. In daily practice, Jhung Rojhung has become a social force that motivates individuals to remain present and useful to others, even in the absence of material rewards. This culture also fosters solidarity among officials. They assist one another in completing tasks when someone is ill and even take on a colleague's responsibilities when they are facing family

issues, without complaint. This phenomenon demonstrates that the spirit of altruism that emerges is not driven by a reward-based management system but rather by a cultural obligation to uphold one's reputation, create harmony, and build solidarity within the workplace community.

This phenomenon highlights the importance of understanding that in a society such as Madura, work ethics cannot be separated from moral and cultural dimensions. Altruism cannot be separated from the value system that provides meaning to helping others. In this case, *Jhung Rojhung* acts as a social glue that makes work and kindness a part of a dignified existence. When village officials feel that they are part of a mutually dependent and morally accountable social network, helping others becomes part of their social identity. The implication of this finding is that, in a village context, policies to improve the performance of officials do not always have to rely on material reward systems. Building awareness of values and strengthening cultural symbols, such as *Jhung Rojhung*, can be an effective strategy to encourage proactive, collaborative, and dedicated work behaviour. This also challenges public management approaches that overly emphasise instrumental rationality and formalistic logic, opening up space for more humanistic and value-based approaches. Thus, *Jhung Rojhung* not only evokes a sense of individual responsibility but also binds individuals to a deep sense of social responsibility. This value transcends formal work norms and shapes interaction patterns based on a sense of belonging and mutual care. Within the framework of OCB, this shows how local culture can be a transformative force that drives voluntary, unpressured, unrewarded, yet meaningful work behaviours.

Loyalty and Conscientiousness

In the context of village organisational behaviour in Madura, loyalty and conscientiousness emerge as the main expressions of *Jhung Rojhung*, which has transformed into a concrete form of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). Loyalty is a moral bond to leaders and the community, as well as loyalty to the village government's position or formal structure. Village officials involved in this study demonstrated high dedication to leaders (village heads) and the government structure, not merely because of administrative contracts but because of respect for the social and spiritual order attached to leadership positions. A village head stated, "Once the community trusts us and elects us as village heads, we must be ready whenever needed. There are no days off when the community calls."

Jhung Rojhung's values in this case reinforce the element of conscientiousness, which is behaviour that goes beyond formal responsibilities to maintain the continuity of public services. This is evident in work routines that know no time limits, regularity in documenting residents' needs, and caution in making decisions regarding village funds or programmes. Some administrative staff, for example, show personal initiative to learn how to use financial and village administration applications, even though this is not explicitly required, because they feel responsible for maintaining public trust. This reflects the dimension of conscientiousness in OCB as described by Organ (1988): employees who show high attention to order, accuracy, and timeliness as a form of commitment to the organisation. This loyalty is often inseparable from the patron-client relationship system characteristic of Madurese culture, where the village head is positioned as a central figure who must be respected but also protected. For most officials, maintaining the reputation of leaders is not merely a professional obligation but also a matter of family and social honour. Thus, OCB in the form of loyalty becomes a "moral debt"

that is continuously repaid through work commitment, even in situations of resource constraints or social pressure.

However, this loyalty is not without its potential dilemmas. On the one hand, it strengthens solidarity and internal order within the village organisation. However, when loyalty is misused to justify the tolerance of inequality or abuse of authority, Jhung Rojhung can become a justification for a culture of silence. This is where conscientiousness plays a critical role as a counterbalance: loyal and integrity-driven officials will still report or reprimand colleagues who deviate, as they consider it their moral responsibility. Thus, Jhung Rojhung culturally reinforces two important dimensions of OCB: loyalty as a meaningful value-based commitment and integrity, and conscientiousness manifested in perseverance, discipline, and a strong sense of responsibility toward public service at the grassroots level.

Harmony and Civic Virtue

The value of Jhung Rojhung also plays an important role in creating and maintaining social harmony at the village level, which is closely correlated with the dimension of civic virtue in the OCB framework. In this context, civic virtue is understood as the active involvement of individuals in the collective life of organisations and society, as well as the willingness to uphold social norms, values, and stability. In the context of village communities, characterised by face-to-face interactions and intense social connectedness, harmony is not merely a shared ideal but a basic necessity for social relations to remain productive and free from horizontal conflict.

The value of Jhung Rojhung emphasises the importance of maintaining respect, manners, and social obligations towards fellow citizens, especially in public spaces. In practice, this can be seen from the active participation of village officials in community activities outside working hours, such as mutual assistance, tahlilan, RT arisan, and informal meetings among village leaders. Their presence is not merely a symbol of formal government representation but a sign that they are “part of the community”, not separate entities. As one informant stated, “If I do not attend village meetings or night patrols, the residents will feel that I do not care. However, that’s important for maintaining relationships.” In village deliberations, for example, village officials actively seek to create a dialogue-based and non-confrontational atmosphere in the village. They engage in discussions without imposing their opinions, attempting to find common ground between the aspirations of residents and the limitations of the village bureaucracy. This reflects civic virtue in its deliberative dimension: respect for the plurality of voices in public decision-making. Even in conflicts between residents, some hamlet heads admit that they often act as informal mediators who prioritise a family-orientated approach over formal legal channels. Jhung Rojhung also encourages preventive measures against potential conflicts. For example, village officials take the initiative to visit residents who are mourning or experiencing economic difficulties, not for bureaucratic intervention, but as a form of cultural solidarity. This practice shows that civic virtue within the Madurese cultural framework is not merely a political act by citizens but an ethical expression of socially embedded cultural values.

However, it should be noted that the tendency to maintain harmony can also lead to compromises that close the space for open criticism and discussion. In some cases, village officials avoid confrontation with residents or fellow officials to maintain a “harmonious” atmosphere, even though there are policies that should be corrected. Civic virtue can become

blunt if it is not supported by the principles of justice and transparency. Overall, Jhung Rojhung expands the meaning of civic virtue from mere formal participation to social sensitivity, active involvement, and ethical concern in maintaining social balance at the community level. It bridges the formality of organisations with the social kinship network characteristics of villages, thereby strengthening the moral foundation of OCB practices in rural governance.

2. Discussion

The findings of this study indicate that the local cultural values of Jhung Rojhung play a key role in shaping the work behaviour of village officials, particularly within the framework of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB). In this section, the findings are interpreted systematically with reference to OCB theories and organisational culture concepts, as presented in the literature review. The primary objective of this discussion is to demonstrate how local values such as Jhung Rojhung are relevant within a specific cultural context and contribute to expanding the theoretical understanding of culturally grounded OCB.

Integration of Local Values into the OCB Dimension

According to Currall and Organ (1988), OCB encompasses five main dimensions: altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, and civic virtue. The findings of this study consistently show that Jhung Rojhung values resonate strongly with four of these five dimensions, particularly altruism, conscientiousness, and civic virtues. Village officials use Jhung Rojhung values as a moral compass to shape their internal perceptions of responsibility and work ethics. Responsibility is no longer viewed as a mere administrative duty but as a moral expression of respect for social position and the trust of the community. (Rolin, 2021) This is highly correlated with the dimension of conscientiousness, where individuals not only carry out formal tasks, but also demonstrate thoroughness and perseverance beyond the written job requirements. (Wilmot & Ones, 2019) On the other hand, Jhung Rojhung also encourages altruistic behaviour. The culture of "doing good so as not to lose one's self-respect" gives rise to an unwritten norm of always being ready to help, especially in social contexts. In the OCB framework, this reflects altruism, that is, helping fellow workers or community members without expecting anything in return. (Klotz et al., 2018). Furthermore, the spirit of maintaining social harmony and involvement in collective activities demonstrates a strong civic virtue. Village officials are actively involved in activities outside formal working hours, including community service, traditional meetings, and social events, as a form of contribution to social sustainability and institutional integrity (Ho & Barton, 2022). Within the OCB framework, this marks the role of active organisation members who are aware of collective interests.

The Role of Culture in Internalising OCB

Organisational culture theory, as proposed by Schein (2010), states that core values embedded in an organisation, or in this case, a community, shape the mindset and behaviour of its members. Jhung Rojhung can be positioned as a cultural artefact that shapes basic assumptions about "what is good and right" when behaving as a public servant. This is in line with Schein's layers of organisational culture: (1) artefacts (customs of mutual assistance in village activities), (2) values (respect for position, maintaining the good name of the family and village), and (3) basic assumptions (self-esteem is attached to social contribution and obedience to the social hierarchy). Village officials who uphold Jhung Rojhung do not merely obey bureaucratic rules; they feel that their personal identity and social honour are at stake through

the quality of service they provide. Thus, OCB behaviour does not occur in a vacuum. It is embedded in the context of local values and norms that indirectly shape individuals' motivations, orientations, and self-perceptions in their organisational roles.

Hofstede and Local Cultural Dimensions

Gibson (1990) introduces six dimensions of national culture, two of which are most relevant in this context: power distance and collectivism. Madurese society exhibits strong characteristics of high-power distance, where social structures are highly hierarchical and respect for authority is an important norm. In this context, *Jhung Rojhung* reinforces loyalty towards leaders (reflected in the conscientiousness dimension) as part of a system of honour that must be upheld. Additionally, social practices like mutual assistance and active participation in village activities reflect collectivist values. Village officials do not see themselves merely as individuals with administrative roles but as part of an interdependent social network. This strengthens participation in civic activities and increases the likelihood of OCB emerging sustainably because it is supported by collective social norms rather than employment contracts. (Siswandani & Prasetyo, 2022) (Luo et al., 2024). From this perspective, *Jhung Rojhung* acts as a bridge between the community's collective values and the formal bureaucratic role played by village officials. In the Philippines, culture reinforces concrete manifestations of OCB, such as loyalty, willingness to help, perseverance, and awareness of community harmony. (Diansari et al., 2023).

Contribution to the Expansion of OCB Theory

Most OCB literature is based on the context of modern organisations in the private sector and assumes a more individualistic and rational Western work culture. (Grego-Planer, 2019) However, this study indicates that OCB can also thrive in local contexts with very different cultural structures. These findings suggest the need to expand OCB theory into the dimension of "cultural-embedded OCB", where extra-role behaviour is motivated not only by internal factors (e.g., job satisfaction or organisational commitment) but also by normative and symbolic cultural values. (Deshmukh & Natu, 2023; Rao et al., 2022b) In this case, *Jhung Rojhung* is not only a local value, but also a cultural script that regulates social relations and moral responsibilities within the organisation. The theoretical implication of these findings is that OCB theory should begin to consider cultural factors as important variables rather than mere background factors. Local values such as *Jhung Rojhung* indicate that organizational behavior cannot always be understood solely through individualistic or structuralistic frameworks but must also be understood through symbolic and cultural frameworks.

5. CONCLUSION

This study examines the role of local cultural values, *Jhung Rojhung*, in shaping organisational behaviour, particularly *Organisational Citizenship Behaviour* (OCB), among village officials in Madura. A qualitative case study in Padelegan Village, Pamekasan, found that *Jhung Rojhung* is not merely a social norm but functions as a moral compass, guiding the attitudes and actions of village officials in public service. These values foster responsibility, altruistic concern, loyalty, caution, and efforts to maintain social harmony key dimensions of OCB, such as altruism, conscientiousness, and civic virtue. These findings suggest that OCB in the local context is not merely rooted in modern values or organisational incentives but is embedded in a strong traditional cultural structure. Thus, *Jhung Rojhung* serves as a collective ethic that

integrates traditional values with contemporary organisational practice. It intrinsically guides work behaviour, making OCB an expression of social relations, moral consciousness, and communal bonds rather than the result of formal organisational rules. The main theoretical contribution of this study lies in the expansion of OCB theory to be more contextual and inclusive, particularly in the Global South. This study challenges the dominance of Western value-based management theory, which tends to emphasise individual rationality and instrumentalism. Instead, we have shown that collectivist values and relational morality serve as strong foundations for the emergence of consistent OCB in the village public sector. In practical terms, the values of *Jhung Rojhung* can be used as a reference for the recruitment, training, and strengthening of the work ethic of village officials. Local value-based training programmes, such as community-based learning, can strengthen work ethics and organisational cohesion. In addition, village policies should provide space for the expression of local values in work routines and deliberative forums, which also strengthens legitimacy in the eyes of the community. However, this study has contextual limitations, as it was conducted in only one village. Further research could expand the geographical scope, compare local cultures (e.g., gotong royong or mapalus), and adopt a quantitative approach to statistically measure the influence of cultural value internalisation on OCB dimensions.

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